

Anti-Homomorphism in Fuzzy Ideals

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Abstract—The anti-homomorphic image of fuzzy ideals, fuzzy ideals of near-rings and anti ideals are discussed in this note. A necessary and sufficient condition has been established for near-ring anti ideal to be characteristic.

Keywords—Fuzzy Ideals, Anti fuzzy subgroup, Anti fuzzy ideals, Anti homomorphism, Lower α level cut.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN 1971, Rosenfeld [11] constituted the elementary concepts of fuzzy subgroupoid, fuzzy ideals and fuzzy subgroups. Biswas [3] introduced the notion of anti fuzzy subgroups. Fuzzy subnear-rings are introduced by Abou-Zaid [1]. He studied fuzzy left (resp. right) ideals of a near-ring and gave some properties of fuzzy prime ideals of a near-ring. In [7], it has been established that homomorphic image of a fuzzy left (resp. right) ideal which has "sup property" is a fuzzy left (resp. right) ideal. In the year 1998, Sung M.H. et al. [12] proved the same result using the level fuzzy subsets and obtained some properties based on near-ring homomorphism. Properties of anti-homomorphic images of near-rings are discussed in [5]. Homomorphic images and pre images of anti fuzzy ideals are investigated by K.H. Kim et al. [9]. The notion of anti homomorphic image and pre image of fuzzy and anti fuzzy ideals are investigated in this paper. Also, near-ring anti homomorphic image and pre image of ideals are obtained.

A. Preliminaries

In this section, review of fuzzy set theoretic concepts are given briefly (for details one can refer [4], [11] and [10]). A fuzzy set μ of a set N is a function $\mu : N \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

μ will be called a fuzzy left ideal [11], if $\mu(xy) \geq \mu(y)$; a fuzzy right ideal, if $\mu(xy) \geq \mu(x)$; anti fuzzy left ideal [3] if $\mu(xy) \leq \mu(y)$; anti fuzzy right ideal, if $\mu(xy) \leq \mu(x)$;

Let $f : N \rightarrow N'$ be a function and let μ and ν be fuzzy sets in N and N' respectively. Then $f(\mu)$ [11], the image of μ under f is a fuzzy set in N' defined by

$$f(\mu)(y) = \begin{cases} \sup \{ \mu(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y) \} & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) \neq \phi \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$$

for all $y \in N'$. $f^{-1}(\nu)$ [11], the preimage of ν under f is a fuzzy set in N given by

$$f^{-1}(\nu)(x) = \nu(f(x))$$

for all $x \in N$.

Similar to an α level cut [4], we have lower level cut [9] as follows:

Let μ be a fuzzy set in a set N . For $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, the lower α level cut of μ is denoted by ${}_{\alpha}N_{\mu}$ and is given by

$${}_{\alpha}N_{\mu} = \{n \in N : \mu(n) \leq \alpha\}.$$

Definition 1.1: [1], [7] Let N be a left near-ring and μ be a non empty fuzzy sub set of N . μ is said to be a fuzzy left N -ideal if

- I-1. $\mu(x - y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$,
- I-2. $\mu(xy) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in N$,
- I-3. $\mu(y + x - y) \geq \mu(x)$ and
- I-4. $\mu(xy) \geq \mu(y)$ where $x, y \in N$

are satisfied. If axioms (I-1), (I-2), (I-3) with

- I-5. $\mu((x + z)y - xy) \geq \mu(z)$

holds, μ is a fuzzy right N -ideal.

From the definition of right near-ring [6], ideals can be defined as follows:

Definition 1.2: Let N be a right near-ring and μ be a non empty fuzzy sub set of N . μ is said to be a fuzzy left N -ideal if (I-1), (I-2), (I-3) and

- I-6. $\mu(xy) \geq \mu(y)$ where $x, y \in N$

are satisfied. If (I-7) is postulated instead of (I-5) of fuzzy N -ideal of left near-ring, μ is a fuzzy right N -ideal where

- I-7. $\mu(y(x + z) - yx) \geq \mu(z)$.

Definition 1.3: [9] Let N be a left near-ring and μ be a non empty fuzzy sub set of N . μ is said to be an anti fuzzy left N -ideal if

- AI-1. $\mu(x - y) \leq \max\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$,
- AI-2. $\mu(xy) \leq \max\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$,
- AI-3. $\mu(y + x - y) \leq \mu(x)$ and
- AI-4. $\mu(xy) \leq \mu(x)$ where $x, y \in N$.

If axioms (AI-1), (AI-2), (AI-3) with the following (AI-5) are satisfied then μ is an anti fuzzy right N -ideal;

- AI-5. $\mu((x + z)y - xy) \leq \mu(z)$.

Definition 1.4: Let N be a right near-ring and μ be a non empty fuzzy sub set of N . μ is said to be an anti fuzzy left N -ideal when AI-1 to AI-3 along with

- AI-6. $\mu(xy) \leq \mu(y)$ where $x, y \in N$

are postulated. If axioms (AI-1), (AI-2), (AI-3) with (AI-7) are satisfied then μ is an anti fuzzy right N -ideal;

- AI-7. $\mu(y(x + z) - yx) \leq \mu(z)$.

Recall that, a function $f : N \rightarrow N'$ of near-rings is called an **anti-homomorphism** [5] when

1. $f(n + m) = f(m) + f(n)$
2. $f(nm) = f(m)f(n)$, for all $n, m \in N$.

A surjective anti-homomorphism is called an **anti-epimorphism** (\cong).

II. MAIN RESULTS

A. Fuzzy Ideals

It is to be noted that the anti homomorphic image pre-image of a fuzzy groupoid is again a fuzzy groupoid. Where as,

Result 2.1: An anti homomorphic pre-image of a right (left) ideal is a left (right) ideal.

Proof: Let ν be a fuzzy left ideal. Then

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(xy) &= \nu(f(xy)) \\ &= \nu(f(y)f(x)) \\ &\geq \nu(f(x)) \\ &= \mu(x),\end{aligned}$$

a right ideal. When ν is a fuzzy right ideal,

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(xy) &= \nu(f(xy)) \\ &= \nu(f(y)f(x)) \\ &\geq \nu(f(y)) \\ &= \mu(y),\end{aligned}$$

a left ideal. \square

Result 2.2: Anti-homomorphic image of a fuzzy left (right) ideal, with spermium property, is a fuzzy right (left) ideal.

Proof: Let μ be a fuzzy left ideal with sup property. Given $f(x), f(y)$ in $f(N)$, let $x_0 \in f^{-1}[f(x)], y_0 \in f^{-1}[f(y)]$ be such that

$$\mu(x_0) = \sup_{t \in f^{-1}[f(x)]} \mu(t), \quad \mu(y_0) = \sup_{t \in f^{-1}[f(y)]} \mu(t)$$

respectively. Then

$$\begin{aligned}\nu[f(x)f(y)] &= \nu[f(yx)] \\ &= \sup_{t \in f^{-1}[f(yx)]} \mu(t) \\ &\geq \mu(y_0x_0) \\ &\geq \mu(x_0) \\ &= \sup_{t \in f^{-1}[f(x)]} \mu(t) \\ &= \nu[f(x)],\end{aligned}$$

implies ν is a fuzzy right ideal. Similarly, when μ is a fuzzy right ideal with above property, we have ν is a fuzzy left ideal. \square

In sequel to the above results, the following also can be established for the case of anti fuzzy left (right) ideals.

Result 2.3: An anti homomorphic pre-image of an anti fuzzy right (left) ideal is an anti fuzzy left (right) ideal.

Result 2.4: An anti homomorphic image of an anti fuzzy right (left) ideal with sup property, is an anti fuzzy left (right) ideal.

B. Fuzzy Ideals in Near-rings

Result 2.5: ([5] Theorem 2.2) Anti homomorphic image of a right near-ring (left near-ring) is a left near-ring (right near-ring).

Result 2.6: Let $f : N \rightarrow N'$ be an anti-epimorphism of near-rings. If ν is a fuzzy (left/right) ideal in the right (left) near-ring N' , then μ , which is $f^{-1}(\nu)$ is a fuzzy (left/right) ideal in the left (right) near-ring N .

Proof:

Let ν be a fuzzy left ideal of right near-ring N' . The proof of conditions (I-1), (I-2) and (I-3) of definition 1.1 are similar to that of proof of [7] Theorem 2.12. For any $x, y \in N$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(xy) &= \nu(f(xy)) \\ &= \nu(f(y)f(x)) \\ &\geq \nu(f(y)) \\ &= \mu(y).\end{aligned}$$

Thus μ is a fuzzy left ideal of the left near-ring N . When ν is a right ideal of right near-ring N' , for any $x, y, z \in N$ we have,

$$\begin{aligned}\mu((x+z)y - xy) &= \nu(f((x+z)y - xy)) \\ &= \nu(f(y)f(x+z) - f(xy)) \\ &= \nu(f(y)(f(x) + f(z)) - f(y)f(x)) \\ &\geq \nu(f(z)) \\ &= \mu(z),\end{aligned}$$

μ is a fuzzy right ideal of left near-ring N .

Let ν be a right ideal of left near-ring N' . For any $x, y, z \in N$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(y(x+z) - yx) &= \nu(f((x+z)y - xy)) \\ &= \nu(f(x+z)f(y) - f(yx)) \\ &= \nu((f(x) + f(z))f(y) - f(x)f(y)) \\ &\geq \nu(f(z)) \\ &= \mu(z).\end{aligned}$$

Thus μ is a fuzzy left ideal of right near-ring N . Let ν is a fuzzy left ideal of left near-ring N' . Then

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(xy) &= \nu(f(xy)) \\ &= \nu(f(y)f(x)) \\ &\geq \nu(f(x)) \\ &= \mu(x)\end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y \in N$, implies μ is a left ideal of right near ring N . \square

Result 2.7: Let $f : N \rightarrow N'$ be an anti-epimorphism of near-rings. If μ is a fuzzy (left/right) ideal in the left (right) near-ring N with sup property, then $\nu = f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy (left/right) ideal in the right (left) near-ring N' .

Proof: Let μ be a fuzzy left ideal of the left near-ring N with sup property and ν be the image of μ under f . Let $x_0 \in f^{-1}[f(x)]$, $y_0 \in f^{-1}[f(y)]$ such that

$$\mu(x_0) = \sup_{t \in f^{-1}[f(x)]} \mu(t), \quad \mu(y_0) = \sup_{t \in f^{-1}[f(y)]} \mu(t).$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nu[f(x)f(y)] &= \sup_{t \in f^{-1}[f(yx)]} \mu(t) \\ &\geq \mu(y_0x_0) \\ &\geq \mu(x_0) \\ &= \sup_{t \in f^{-1}[f(x)]} \mu(t) \\ &= \nu[f(x)]. \end{aligned}$$

That is ν is a fuzzy left ideal of right near-ring N' .

If μ is a fuzzy right ideal of left near-ring. For any $f(z) \in f(N)$, let $z_0 \in f^{-1}[f(z)]$ such that

$$\mu(z_0) = \sup_{t \in f^{-1}[f(z)]} \mu(z).$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} &\nu\{f\{(x+z)y - (xy)\}\} \\ &= \nu\{f(y)f(x+z) - f(xy)\} \\ &= \nu\{f(y)\{f(x) + f(z)\} - f(y)f(x)\} \\ &= \sup_{t \in f^{-1}\{f\{f(y)\{f(x)+f(z)\} - f(y)f(x)\}\}} \mu(t) \\ &\geq \mu\{y_0\{x_0 + z_0\} - y_0x_0\} \\ &\geq \mu\{z_0\} \\ &= \sup_{t \in f^{-1}[f(z)]} \mu(t) \\ &= \nu\{f(z)\}. \end{aligned}$$

That is, ν is a fuzzy right ideal of right near-ring.

The image and pre-image of the fuzzy ideal of a fuzzy right near-ring N can be proved to be the fuzzy ideal of a left near-ring N' . \square

C. Anti Fuzzy Ideals in Near-rings

Definition 2.8: A left N -ideal A of a near-ring is said to be characteristic [2], [8] if

$$f(A) = A \quad \forall f \in \text{Aut}(N)$$

where $\text{Aut}(N)$ is set of all automorphism of N .

Anti fuzzy left N -ideal of μ of a near-ring N is said to be anti fuzzy characteristic if

$$\mu f(x) = \mu(x) \quad \forall x \in N, f \in \text{Aut}(N).$$

Lemma 2.9: Let μ be an anti fuzzy left N -ideal of a near-ring N and let $x \in N$. Then $\mu(x) = s$ if and only if $x \in {}_sN_\mu$ and $x \notin {}_tN_\mu \quad \forall s > t$.

Proof is obvious.

The proof of the following theorem is analogous to the proof of theorem 3.9 [2], [8].

Theorem 2.10: Let μ be an anti fuzzy N -ideal of a near-ring N . Then each lower α level left N -ideal of μ is characteristic iff μ is an anti fuzzy characteristic of N .

K. H. Kim et al. [9] proved the following theorems:

Result 2.11 ([9], Theorem 3.19 (1)): Let $f : N \rightarrow N'$ be an epimorphism of near-rings. Let ν be an anti-fuzzy left N' -ideal and μ be the pre-image of ν under f . Then μ is an anti-fuzzy left N -ideal.

Result 2.12 ([9], Theorem 3.19 (2)): Let $f : N \rightarrow N'$ be a surjective homomorphism of near-rings. If μ is an anti fuzzy left N' -ideal then $f^{-1}(\mu)$ is an anti fuzzy left N -ideal.

Result 2.13: Let $f : N \rightarrow N'$ be an anti-epimorphism of near-rings. Let ν be an anti-fuzzy (left/right) ideal of right (left) near-ring N' then μ , the pre-image of ν under f , is an anti-fuzzy (left/right) ideal of left (right) near-ring N .

The proof of AI-4 and AI-5 are similar to the proof of result 2.6.

Result 2.14: Let $f : N \rightarrow N'$ be an anti epimorphism. If μ is an anti fuzzy (left/right) ideal of left (right) near-ring N with sup property, $f(\mu)$ is an anti fuzzy (left/right) ideal of right (left) near-ring N' .

The proof of AI-6 and AI-7 are similar to that of result 2.7.

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